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Research Article

ALLEVIATING STRESS IN WORKPLACE¹Noreen Shahbaz, ²Ms. Sana Sehar, ³Muhammad Afzal, ⁴Dr. Syed Amir Gilani.

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Article Received: October 2019**Accepted:** November 2019**Published:** December 2019**Abstract:****Background:**

Nurses especially female nurses are under a great deal of stress related to a variety of occupational, organization, socio-demographic and psychographic stressors. Occupational stressors contribute to organizational inefficiency, high staff turnover, absenteeism due to sickness, decreased quality, and quantity of practice, increased costs of health care, and decreased job satisfaction. One of the organizational outcomes that affected by occupational stress is job performance.

Purpose: *The purpose of this study to investigate the effect of job stress on job performance.*

Methods: *The universe of the study is Tertiary Hospital, is a descriptive and exploratory analysis of a person.*

Results: *The analysis showed that there is an inverse relationship between job stress factors and job performance indicating that there is high job stress in the staff nurses, resulting in low job performance, depression, emotional exhaustion and anxiety and different problems may effect on work.*

Conclusion: *Correct stress management should start from improved health and good intrapersonal relationships. The prevention and management of workplace stress requires organizational level interventions, because it is the organization that creates the stress. Success in managing and preventing stress will depend on the culture in the organization. Those staff nurses who had high level of job stress had low job performance.*

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INTRODUCTION:**1.1a CASE SCENARIO****INCIDENT:**

Ms X was a new joiner and started her job as a staff nurse in private hospital. It was first experience of her job and she was very confused and in stress related to organizational, occupational, socio-demographic and psychographic factors in hospital. As well as three nurses also with her and they were all new joiner in this hospital. After passing some time their ward manger called in her office and introduces herself. They told her ward manager that they were very worried and in stress related to inter personal conflicts, death and dying and no experience in any work place, overload working time and duty works, surrounding by annoyed employees, lacking time for scheduling, and absenteeism of coworkers.

Ward manager was very cooperative and she encouraged them and builds up a good relationship with effective communication. She told them how to deal with stress and cope them. She provided them friendly policies reduce the stress such as provide adequate opportunities for breaks and meals and provide adequate time for important function of the organization. She told some strategies that are directed at actuality able to minimize and change stressful environment.

Stress related to:

1. Occupational
2. Organizational
3. Socio-demographic
4. Psychographic

Occupational Factors	Organizational Factors	Socio-demographic Factors	Psychographic Factors
Workload, high demands for work, tension relationship between nurse and doctor, insufficient personnel and lack of resources, conflict between staff and intergroup, and uncertainty of position.	Administration and management, lack of concern, poor relationship support	Gender Variances (female/male), Age Variances, knowledge Role and experience	Moral tolerance, burden of conscience life and mortality, family members and patients who are uncooperative

Organizational factors:

Nursing management has shown that the stress, management and organizational obligations are another significant source of stress among nurses in the development process. Organizational variables include staff nurses, supervisors, and head nurses. Poor management may leads to misunderstanding of position, shortage of resources such as scarcity of personnel which causes workload, tension, and division between nurses which impact patient care and decision making.

Occupational factors:

Occupational factors play an important role in the development of nurses ' stress process. Work demands, nurse-physician working interactions, insufficient personnel and lack of resources, interpersonal / intergroup tension and position

uncertainty are the workplace factors that cause stress.

Factors related Socio demographic:

Stress-related socio-demographic elements including age and gender. More than males, females have encountered stress and stress has also been recorded among younger nurses than once. In addition, experiencing the stress level among newly graduated nurses is increasing.

Psychographic Factors:

Psychographic factors are correlated with stress levels among nurses, these stressors are the passive pressure of dealing with death and dying, lack of self-confidence, dealing with no cooperative patients/ clients, family members etc.

1.1b Problem solving strategies:

The ward manager adapted to some strategies to respond to certain approaches to minimise the effect of stress between nurses. Since organizational strategies can reduce stress and cope with stress level.

Provide suitable working conditions and climate for establishing specific professional responsibilities, such as creating a good atmosphere.

Managing role means having effective communication and discussion between healthcare employees and patients in particular and offering a positive re-evaluation.

Provide guidance that is necessary to be present in stressful situations as nurses at certain times feel they want to be 'seen' or 'heard' that helps to decrease feelings of undervaluing.

Provide them relief stressors environment/ Provide friendly environment.

She built a work environment that was welcoming. Working in a relaxed and well-organized atmosphere thus estimate perceived levels of trust, encouragement, incentives and better communication among the organization employees and clients.

Give support and encourage them. Consequently, social support can decrease the stress level. Stress management is linked to the need for social support in which includes friends, family members, and colleagues. Nurses who receive social reinforcement from various sources (e.g. parents, family, and colleagues) are more likely to be able to balance their demands for stress and work.

She also implemented supporting policies such as resolution to facilitate wellorganized coordination and to establish reliable nursing services.

MANAGEMENT PROCESS:

- a. Organizational stress management theory
- b. Transactional model of stress and coping

**A. ORGANIZATIONAL STRESS MANAGEMENT THEORY
(MODERN MANAGEMENT THEORY)**

Organizational Methods (Modern management theory)
 Communication and social support can reduce stress as well.
 Open up and down channels of communication.
 Open communication eliminates distrust and speculation.
 Team building allows workers to create support networks between themselves.
 Employee supportive strategies reduce stress such as:
 Providing satisfactory opportunities for meal.
 Provide sufficient time for the organization's important function

B. TRANSACTIONAL MODEL OF STRESS AND COPING

Concept	Definition	Application
Primary Appraisal	Assessment of the importance of a stressor, a condition that threatens or challenges	Understanding the incident as a risk may cause anxiety and discomfort.
Secondary Appraisal	Assessment in handling the stressor and the assets of a person	Understanding the willingness of the individual to make changes to the situation, control the emotional experience of the person and/or actively deal with it can contribute to positive coping and adaptation
Coping efforts	Clear methods for mediating primary and secondary assessments (appraisals)	
Problem Management	Strategies and preparations for improving the stressful event	Effective handling, problem solving, and looking for useful information.
Emotional Regulation	Strategies or strategies to change the way people think and feel about a stressful event	It is possible to apply free expression to strong emotions, actions, indifference, rejection, or finding social support.
Managing-based coping	Coping to actions involving good feelings and emotions that in effect help the cycle of coping physically and mentally by giving the opportunity to represent the issue in various appraisals	Positive reappraisal, positive incidents, reconsideration of plans for change
Outcomes of coping (adaptation)	Emotionally well-being, positive attitude, good actions	The short- and long-term effects of coping strategies can be changed positively as well as negatively.
Dispositional coping styles	Through forms of behaving that may influence the physical and emotional reaction of a person to the stressor.	
Information seeking	Attentional style that are attentive (monitoring) and those that are related to evasion (blunting)	Monitoring can increase anxiety and vigilance; effective coping could also be collected. Blunting may raise concerns but may also reduce obligation and responsibilities.
Optimism	Brings positive outcomes and performance standards	Optimists can report less symptoms or rapid disease recovery.

(Adapted from Glanz & Schwartz, 2015. health behavior and health education. Theory, Research, and Practice)

A.

FIGURE 10.1. DIAGRAM OF TRANSACTIONAL MODEL OF STRESS AND COPING.

(Transactional model)

B.

(Modern management theory evaluation)

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK:
Transactional Stress Model is the framework of

managing and coping with stress events to determine stressful situations. The Transactional Model is a

method that provides an overview of stress and how to usage coping strategies to promote health education, health elevation and prevention from disease. In fact, recognizing this stress and stress coping concept is important to designing effective approaches and solutions for staff nurses and health care providers to improve functioning and support physiological, and emotional well-being. This theory concept is one of the greatest effective methods for mental stress and stress coping.

Another study reflected stress to be transactional miracle among the person and the environment. The concept of this theory is to describe the process of an adult which involves behavioral tests and responses to coping. Evaluations may be percipient and impercipient, or subjective, spatial, and variables may influence them. Coping is the physiological as well as psychological effort to make problem more comfortable and controllable.

According to this Transactional Mode, assessments are classified into Primary and Secondary, where a person faces a stressful situation, is called upon to evaluate risks, hazards or difficulties (Primary Assessment) and is able to switch and improve that situation and switch negative emotional reactions (Secondary Assessment).

In turn, this theory reveals nurses' causes of workplace stress and they use coping strategies to handle multiple (external or internal) stressors-related demands.

DISCUSSION:

(Cause and effects)

Some results revealed that the main causes why nurses have high level of stress accompanied by institutional reasons are occupational factors. Therefore, job exhaustion was the most common of all workplace stressors experienced by most nurses (Mazzella Ebstein.,2019).

Research found that job requirements / overload work were the biggest factors of psychological and physical health resulting in depression, emotional exhaustion and anxiety amongst nurses in specialty nursing practices (Gomes et al., 2016).

The work environment plays an important role in the stress experiences of the participants. In general, workload and nurses shortages, psychological pressures, lack of social care, language barriers and as well as lack of respect on the part of patients and family fellows and cultural differences have been established as causes of work related stress that

support the theory (stresses arising from experiences between persons and workplace). A stressor has been viewed as any activity, circumstance or entity that an individual can encounter in atmosphere requiring change and adaptation. Moreover model offered a framework for understanding the stressors of nurses. (Wazqar et al.,2017).

In additional research study done by Bardeh et al. (2016), explore that weak relationships with colleagues are the greatest source of work stress among nurses. It could due to differences in healthcare systems, facilities styles (public versus private). Nonetheless, researchers suggested that nurses with a larger workload and shortage of nursing staff are vulnerable to negative results, including greater levels of stress and anxiety.

Nwozichi and Ojewole (2015) also showed that Support from healthcare system and nursing management can act as bridge to minimize work stress and maintain nurses' safety. Another studies also focused specifically on work stress due to lack of social support between nurses.

CONCLUSION:

Nursing management has shown that the stress, management and organizational obligations are another significant source of stress among nurses in the development process. Correct stress management should start from improved health and good intrapersonal relationships. The prevention and management of workplace stress requires organizational level interventions, because it is the organization that creates the stress. Such as some stress management strategies to respond to certain approaches to minimize the effect of stress between nurses. Since organizational strategies can reduce stress and cope with stress level. Success in managing and preventing stress will depend on the culture in the organization. Those staff nurses who had high level of job stress had low job performance.

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